

Increasing the efficacy of abiraterone - from pharmacokinetics, through therapeutic drug monitoring to overcoming food effects with innovative pharmaceutical products

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ABSTRACT

Current guidelines suggest radiotherapy as a first-line treatment for prostate cancer, along with prostatectomy, and androgen deprivation therapy. Abiraterone is a first-in-class medicinal product recommended in the treatment of metastatic castration resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC) that targets androgen receptors and inhibits systemic synthesis. However, successful therapy with this drug may pose some challenges. It has to be administered as an inactive prodrug - abiraterone acetate. It is also dissolved and absorbed poorly with large inter-individual variability and exhibits considerable food effects. Additionally, the recommended daily dose of the drug is high (1000 mg abiraterone acetate), and the cost of the therapy is burdensome.

The following review focuses on the strategies to optimize therapy with abiraterone acetate. First, it summarizes current findings on abiraterone pharmacokinetics and accentuates the need for utilizing therapeutic monitoring in clinical practice. Next, it extensively describes the options for improving the low bioavailability of the drug. The two major approaches are the utilization of the positive food effect to increase the exposure and development of supergenerics. The review emphasizes how different formulation approaches lead to increased solubility and impact the outcomes of pre-clinical and clinical trials. The review concludes with a discussion on possible future directions that may lead to the increase of the therapeutic efficacy of abiraterone.

1. Introduction

As of 2020, the Global Cancer Observatory (GLOBOCAN), a World Health Organization initiative, lists prostate cancer as one of the most prevalent malignancies in males (World Health Organization, 2022). With a 30.7 age-standardized incidence rate per 100,000, it is the second worldwide next to lung cancer. In the developed areas, such as Europe or Northern America, its incidence is the highest, reaching over 60 age-standardized incidence rate per 100,000. Current guidelines suggest radiotherapy as a first-line treatment for prostate cancer, along with prostatectomy and androgen deprivation therapy (ADT) (American Urological Association, 2017; European Association of Urology, 2022). Although ADT successfully suppresses testosterone formation, 10 - 20% of patients are at risk of developing castration-resistant prostate cancer (CRPC), and most of these subjects have metastases present at the time of diagnosis (Kirby et al., 2011). Hence, these patients require concomitant treatment with agents that target the androgen receptor or

inhibit systemic synthesis.

Abiraterone (CB7630), a steroidal compound and a first-in-class drug, exhibits a high affinity to CYP17, with an inhibition constant as low as 0.39 nM (Cheong et al., 2020). This enzyme is critical for the biosynthesis of steroids (Fig. 1). It possesses the functionality of 17-alpha-hydroxylase and 17,20-lyase (Vasaitis et al., 2011). These activities enable the formation of 17-alpha-hydroxypregnenolone and 17-alpha-hydroxyprogesterone, and then dehydroepiandrosterone and androstenedione. The latter is a precursor of testosterone. Abiraterone, dosed orally as an acetate prodrug (abiraterone acetate, AA), effectively decreases testosterone levels in non castrate males by even 50% (O'Donnell et al., 2004). The phase II and phase III clinical trials in patients with CRPC led to EMA's and FDA's approval in 2011, under the brand name Zytiga.

AA exhibits a significant food effect; its increased exposure after the meal influenced strict dosing recommendations by the manufacturer. As the European public assessment report states (European Medicines

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Agency, 2018), Zytiga must be taken as a single dose once daily on an empty stomach or at least two hours after eating food; there is also a strict limitation on the timing of the next meal – it is not allowed sooner than one hour after the drug ingestion. The recommended daily AA dose is as high as 1000 mg to counterbalance a limited absorption in a fasted state. It leads to a considerable cost of a monthly treatment that reaches over 3000 EUR in the European Union (Carl and Vokinger, 2021) and over 10,000 USD in the United States (drugs.com [WWW Document] 2022) for the original formulation. Therefore, the regulators may consider various strategies to make it more accessible to patients while maintaining the probability of therapy success. First, therapeutic drug monitoring allows observing if a patient achieved the target concentration; then, the dosing regimen can be adjusted. Second, considerable food effects that influence AA bioavailability can be utilized to intentionally enhance the absorption, allowing reaching higher exposure or lowering the dose. Third, novel formulations can increase AA solubility in the gastrointestinal tract, elevating its bioavailability and decreasing the dose necessary to achieve the therapeutic goal.

This paper reviews the strategies mentioned above aimed to increase the efficiency of abiraterone. It discusses the clinical effectiveness and describes the drug's pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties. The review serves as a background for further discussion of the therapeutic monitoring strategies, alternative dosing regimens, and novel AA formulations.

2. The place of abiraterone in anticancer therapy

Pivotal phase 3 studies (COU-AA-301 and COU-AA-302) established the place for AA in the management of metastatic CRPC (mCRPC). In men with mCRPC and no prior chemotherapy, AA with prednisone increased the progression-free survival by over eight months compared with prednisone alone (Ryan et al., 2013). The clinical trial on patients previously treated with docetaxel also showed prolonged survival time (14.8 months vs. 10.9 months, $p < 0.001$) and progression-free survival (5.6 months vs. 3.6 months, $p < 0.001$) (de Bono et al., 2011). Another advantage of AA with prednisone was delayed deterioration of health-related quality of life and prolonged time to progression of the worst pain (Basch et al., 2013). As some meta-analyses show, AA with prednisone may also be advantageous for patients with a hormone-sensitive type of metastatic prostate cancer (Rydzewska et al., 2017). The addition of AA to ADT reduced the risk of death by 38% and the progression-free survival, translating to a 28% improvement at three years. Compared to docetaxel, AA with prednisone reduces the risk of death similarly, but is better in increasing the disease progression, has lower toxicity, and offers a higher quality of life (Feyerabend et al., 2018; Kassem et al., 2018). AA was proved to be among the most efficient systemic treatments of mCRPC, with a hazard ratio of 0.61 (95% credible interval, 0.54–0.70) (Wang et al., 2021).

Treatment with AA is not without risks. The odds for serious adverse

Fig. 1. Abiraterone acetate mechanism of action (adapted from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0753332217351661>). Prodrug abiraterone acetate is hydrolyzed to the active moiety - abiraterone. It inhibits CYP17, which catalyzes the synthesis of 17-hydroxypregnenolone, 17-hydroxyprogesterone, DHEA, androstenedione, and testosterone. As a result, the inhibition decreases testosterone levels.

Parts of the figure were drawn by using pictures from Servier Medical Art by Servier is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>). Marvin for Java Script was used for drawing chemical structures, Marvin version 22.11.0, ChemAxon (<https://www.chemaxon.com>).

events increase slightly compared with other available treatments (1.42; 95% CI, 1.10–1.83) (Wang et al., 2021). The most common grade 3–4 adverse events include hypertension, hypokalemia, and edema (Roviello et al., 2016). These are consequences of the inhibited CYP17 pathway. When the levels of cortisol, which is synthesized from 17 α -hydroxypregnenolone and 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone, decrease, the adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH) levels increase (Vasaitis et al., 2011). Without a negative feedback loop, the most prominent symptoms of mineralocorticoid excess manifest. Therefore, the treatment with AA requires concomitant administration of prednisone, 5 or 10 mg BID. Alternatively, dexamethasone might replace prednisone. According to a recent meta-analysis, switching from prednisone to dexamethasone gives more favorable PSA progression rates (Xiong et al., 2021). It may also be an option for patients whose disease progressed during the standard regimen (Yang et al., 2021). Another frequently occurring adverse effect is a significant elevation in transaminase levels and increased risk of cardiac disorders (Iacovelli et al., 2015).

Nevertheless, AA in combination with prednisone or methylprednisolone is a viable therapeutic option for systemic therapy of CRPC, both as a first- and second-line treatment (Mohler et al., 2019).

3. Pharmacokinetics of abiraterone

The typical dosing schedule, as recommended by the manufacturer, assumes 1000 mg AA administered in a single dose under fasting conditions (European Medicines Agency, 2018). Because AA is a prodrug quickly converted to the parental compound, most studies exclusively investigate the main active metabolite - abiraterone. As research results show, AA is hydrolyzed to abiraterone already in the intestinal fluids (Stappaerts et al., 2015). The reaction is enzymatic, and various enzymes are involved in the process, such as pancreatic cholesterol esterase (Basa-Dénes et al., 2019) and arylacetamide deacetylase (Sakai et al., 2021). Thus, hydrolysis occurs in the intestinal lumen and continues in the intestinal and liver microsomes. The absorption occurs rather rapidly. Overall, the concentration reaches maximum values (C_{max}) within two hours on average. However, some studies report maximum values even after 6 h. After a standard 1000 mg dose is administered in fasting conditions, the exposure is approximately 100 - 300 ng/mL for C_{max} , and 600 - 1500 ng·h/mL for the area under the time-concentration curve (AUC). Table 1 presents the main pharmacokinetic parameters calculated by non-compartmental methods in healthy volunteers, while Table 2 presents the data for mCRPC patients.

Reports on the prodrug compound - abiraterone acetate - are rare due to the rapid transformation of AA to abiraterone and very low concentrations of the former. In one study that screened both the parent and metabolite entities, the mean maximum AA concentration in plasma was over 1800-fold lower than the concentration of abiraterone, and over 1000-fold lower mean AUC was reached (Bouhajib and Tayab, 2019). Also, AA reached its maximum concentrations slower (mean t_{max} = 5.53 h) than the metabolite (mean t_{max} = 2.0 h).

A population pharmacokinetic model explained how abiraterone is distributed and eliminated. The model was built from the dataset comprising 95 subjects (62 healthy volunteers and 33 patients with mCRPC) (Stuyckens et al., 2014). Overall, the pharmacokinetics were linear, and a standard two-compartment model best described the drug's disposition. Healthy volunteers eliminated abiraterone faster than mCRPC subjects (apparent clearance 2240 L/h vs. 1505 L/h, for healthy and mCRPC subjects, respectively). The inter-individual variability in clearance was moderate, reaching approximately 30%. Also, the drug had a considerable apparent distribution volume: over 17,000 L for the central compartment and over 5000 L for the peripheral one. These values are a consequence of high affinity to plasma proteins, alpha-1 acid glycoprotein, and albumin. The binding rate is 89.4 to 95.7% for alpha-1 acid glycoprotein and 95.6 to 99.9% for albumin (Center for Drug Evaluation and Research, 2010).

Hepatic and renal impairment can affect abiraterone disposition. In

the study investigating the impact of these comorbidities, subjects with mild hepatic impairment had comparable abiraterone exposure to healthy subjects (Marbury et al., 2014). However, moderate hepatic impairment (Child-Pugh's Class B, score 7–9) decreased abiraterone clearance, leading to a 3.5-fold increase in C_{max} and a 4.8-fold increase in AUC_{0-t} . Therefore, AA should be used with caution in this group, and the manufacturer recommends against using AA when a severe hepatic impairment is present (European Medicines Agency, 2018). In end-stage renal disease patients (with creatinine clearance below 30 mL/min and requiring hemodialysis), C_{max} and AUC of abiraterone were similar to the matched healthy controls. This is in line with the findings of a study with radiolabeled AA showed that the drug is mostly eliminated in feces (Acharya et al., 2013). Up to 50% of the recorded fecal radioactivity arose from unchanged AA and 20% from abiraterone. Only approximately 5% of total radioactivity was recorded in urine, and the majority came from N-oxide abiraterone sulfate. Besides abiraterone, the main abiraterone acetate metabolites are N-oxide and the intermediate compound, abiraterone sulfate. Their exposure is also significantly greater than that of abiraterone, reaching the AUC_{0-8h} of 8000 ng·h/mL for sulfate and 7980 ng·h/mL for N-oxide, respectively. In comparison, abiraterone exposure after the same dose of 1000 mg radio-labeled AA was 74.8 ng·h/mL.

Another metabolic pathway involves 3 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase (3 β -HSD) (Li et al., 2015b). This enzyme converts abiraterone to a 3-keto congener, often labeled Δ^4 -abiraterone (D4A or $\Delta(4)A$). This compound has a similar structure to testosterone and can contribute to the abiraterone's inhibitory effect. Also, D4A appears to have a greater affinity to the androgen receptor and effectively suppresses androgen-responsive gene expression, including PSA (Li et al., 2015b). However, the low D4A's *in vivo* concentrations show considerable intersubject variability, exceeding 61% (Arasaratnam et al., 2019). Several studies compared the exposure of these two compounds. While abiraterone levels, after a standard 1000 mg AA dose, were in the range of 1.5 - 34.01 ng/mL, for D4A they reached only 0.2 - 2.5 ng/mL (Arasaratnam et al., 2019; Kanji et al., 2021); the mean metabolic ratio of D4A/abiraterone is 0.18 +/- 0.25 (Blanchet et al., 2018).

According to the researchers who proposed the population model, the absorption of abiraterone acetate is complex (Stuyckens et al., 2014). It required parametrization with multiple transit compartments. The variability for the apparent bioavailability exceeded 50% in the fasted state, and for the zero-order input, it was over 100%. The most important factor that impacted this process was food. While the absorption duration of an initial zero-order input in fasting conditions was shorter than in the fed state (0.267 h vs. 1.37 h for fasting and low-fat meal, respectively), the presence of food significantly increased AA's bioavailability. When compared with fasted administration, the bioavailability increased by 24% in the modified fasted state, by 280% with a low-fat meal, and by 654% when AA was taken with a high-fat meal. The concomitant food also decreased the inter-individual variability. The impact of coadministration of food is discussed in Chapter 5 of this review.

4. Therapeutic drug monitoring of abiraterone - why and how?

To optimize anticancer therapy, especially for drugs with highly variable pharmacokinetics, clinicians often aim at determining the cut-off point for the drug concentration, above which the treatment efficiency is higher. For abiraterone, such an analysis was conducted using the data from 61 patients with mCRPC undergoing ADT with 1000 mg abiraterone once daily (Carton et al., 2017). The authors compared trough concentrations between responders and non-responders. In responders, defined as individuals whose PSA declined at least 50% after a 3-month therapy, mean C_{min} was significantly greater than in non-responders (12.0 ng/mL vs 8.0 ng/mL, respectively). This finding was reflected in ROC-curve estimated threshold and Kaplan-Meier curves. If abiraterone C_{min} was 8.4 ng/mL or higher, the

Table 1

Abiraterone and abiraterone acetate pharmacokinetic parameters in cancer-free volunteers. For C_{max} and AUC data are presented as means \pm standard deviations, if available; for t_{max} data are presented as medians with minimum-maximum range in brackets.

Number of subjects	Dose[mg]	Prandialstate	C_{max} [ng/ml]	AUC _{0-t} [ng·h/ml]	AUC _{0-∞} [ng·h/ml]	t_{max} [h]	$t_{1/2}$ [h]	Refs.
Abiraterone								
32 total, divided into 4 subgroups	250 - 1000	fasted	250 mg:	Acharya et al. (2013)				
			25.9 \pm 10.0	155 \pm 83.3	162 \pm 84.7	1.75 (1.0, 4.0)	11.1 \pm 2.97	
			500 mg:					
			76.6 \pm 35.9	428 \pm 257	440 \pm 254	2.02 (1.0, 3.0)	14.6 \pm 4.70	
			750 mg:					
			57.4 \pm 32.7	309 \pm 180	317 \pm 183	1.75 (1.0, 3.0)	14.7 \pm 3.96	
33	250 - 1000	fasted	1000 mg:	Acharya et al. (2013)				
			112 \pm 36.7	610 \pm 249	617 \pm 249	1.75 (1.0, 3.0)	12.7 \pm 1.91	
			250 mg:					
			39.9 \pm 25.3	195 \pm 109	210 \pm 105	2.0 (1.0, 6.0)	14.4 \pm 4.5	
			500 mg:					
			67.0 \pm 34.7	336 \pm 156	345 \pm 155	2.0 (1.0, 4.0)	15.3 \pm 4.1	
8 (Study 1), 8 (Study 2), 7 (Study 3)	1000, tablets (Study 1&3) 1000, oral suspension (Study 2)	fasted	750 mg:	Marbury et al. (2014)				
			7.0 \pm 43.3	438 \pm 189	449 \pm 189	2.0 (1.0, 4.0)	16.5 \pm 4.5	
			1000 mg:					
			125 \pm 76.4	607 \pm 298	621 \pm 300	2.0 (1.0, 4.0)	16.0 \pm 4.6	
			Study 1:					
			85.7 \pm 46.6	321 \pm 166	330 \pm 166	1.8 (1.00, 3.00)	13.1 \pm 4.2	
Volunteers with ESRD (ClCr < 30 mL/min), 1000, oral suspension (Study 2)	1000, tablets (Study 1&3) 1000, oral suspension (Study 2)	fasted	Study 2:	Marbury et al. (2014)				
			64.5 \pm 71.0	402 \pm 317	461 \pm 405	1.5 (1.00, 2.00)	15.4 \pm 1.6	
			Study 3:					
			60.6 \pm 23.5	307 \pm 108	315 \pm 108	1.5 (1.00, 4.00)	18.2 \pm 3.7	
			Mild HI:					
			71.9 \pm 40.2	355 \pm 191	365 \pm 194	2.0 (0.50 - 3.00)	17.7 \pm 7.9	
Volunteers with mild HI, moderate HI, and severe HI	1000, oral suspension (Study 2)	fasted	Moderate HI:	Marbury et al. (2014)				
			297 \pm 258	1530 \pm 1350	1562 \pm 1389	1.5 (1.00 - 2.00)	18.6 \pm 5.0	
			Severe HI:					
			12.5 \pm 10.7	189 \pm 140	177 \pm 136	2.0 (1.00 - 6.00)	18.2 \pm 4.8	
			ESRD:	ESRD:	ESRD:	ESRD:	ESRD:	
			50.2 \pm 37.7	305 \pm 267	315 \pm 265	3.0 (1.00 - 6.00)	16.0 \pm 2.0	
35	1000	fasted	70.7 (72) *	–	421 (67)*	–	–	Chi et al. (2015)
			513 (55)*	–	1942 (48)*	–	–	
			1190 (38)*	–	4077 (37)*	–	–	
30 (Japanese descent, Study A, dose escalation) 45 (Caucasian and Japanese descent) (Study B, food effects)	250 - 1000	fasted	Study A	Inoue et al. (2015)				
			250 mg:					
			53.17 \pm 48.58	285.8 \pm 290.52	293.9 \pm 290.25	2.0 (1.0 - 4.0)	14.24 \pm 5.07	
			500 mg:					
			90.46 \pm 74.97	484.4 \pm 435.47	494.3 \pm 434.47	2.0 (1.0 - 4.0)	15.10 \pm 6.11	
			1000 mg:					
172.1 \pm 150.35	810.4 \pm 616.66	822.4 \pm 615.89	1.5 (1.0 - 4.0)	16.59 \pm 6.89				
	1000	fed (MF)	Study B (food effects for a fixed 1000 mg dose)	Study B (food effects for a fixed 1000 mg dose)	Study B (food effects for a fixed 1000 mg dose)	Study B (food effects for a fixed 1000 mg dose)	Study B (food effects for a fixed 1000 mg dose)	
			95.27** (meal 4 h postdose)	534.54** (meal 4 h postdose)	535.1** (meal 4 h postdose)			
			193.36** (meal 1 h postdose)	824.47** (meal 1 h postdose)	841.71** (meal 1 h postdose)			
			972.37** (second meal 4 h postdose)	3817.29** (second meal 4 h postdose)	3720.19** (second meal 4 h postdose)			
			1114.27** (second meal 2 h postdose)	4135.08** (second meal 2 h postdose)	4008.89** (second meal 2 h postdose)			
19	100 - 400 (FPAA) 1000 (originator)	fasted	100 mg:	Goldwater et al. (2017)				
			17.28 \pm 10.41	67.55 \pm 39.37	74.49 \pm 42.22	1.55 \pm 0.57	4.72 \pm 2.57	
			200 mg:					
			9.11 \pm 21.69	169.99 \pm 83.73	\pm 86.70	1.78 \pm 0.77	7.83 \pm 3.88	
			400 mg:					
			5.42 \pm 35.58	302.90 \pm	400 mg: 319.92 \pm 140.74	2.32 \pm 1.33	8.84 \pm 2.96	
1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:				
79.46 \pm 39.56	1000 mg: 387.34 \pm 168.67	421.23 \pm 183.83	2.16 \pm 0.78	14.48 \pm 5.11				
34	125 - 625 (FPAA) 1000 (originator)	fasted	125 mg:	Goldwater et al. (2017)				
			28.22 \pm 16.46	102.55 \pm 63.27	112.12 \pm 65.94	1.5 (0.5 - 4)	7.20 \pm 3.47	
			500 mg:					
			84.16 \pm 44.05	416.23 \pm	438.02 \pm	1.5 (0.5 - 6)	14.12 \pm 6.44	
			625 mg:					
			100.76 \pm 63.75	245.73	249.43	1.5 (0.5 - 4)	14.54 \pm 5.54	
1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:				
83.40 \pm 57.40	450.19 \pm	473.31 \pm	2 (0.5 - 8)	20.64 \pm 9.03				
		241.85						
		1000 mg:		1000 mg:				

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Number of subjects	Dose[mg]	Prandialstate	C _{max} [ng/ml]	AUC _{0-t} [ng·h/ml]	AUC _{0-∞} [ng·h/ml]	t _{max} [h]	t _{1/2} [h]	Refs.	
18	1000	fasted	100.74 ± 50.17	415.91 ± 210.67 499.20 ± 305.19	453.18 ± 219.07 512.47 ± 312.57	2.00 (1.00–6.00)	13.68 ± 3.46	Bouhajib and Tayab (2019) Feng et al. (2022)	
16	75 - 450 AA with SNAC	fasted	75 mg: 33.9 ± 12.9 150 mg: 81.4 ± 45.0 300 mg: 209 ± 142 450 mg: 405 ± 428	75 mg: 98.96 ± 46.29 150 mg: 246.11 ± 97.19 300 mg: 620.08 ± 370.19 450 mg: 370.19 450 mg: 1041.37 ± 903.24	75 mg: 101.27 ± 46.61 150 mg: 250.27 ± 97.95 300 mg: 627.60 ± 370.44 450 mg: 1054.58 ± 904.86	75 mg: 1.13 (0.5–2.5) 150mg: 1.0 (0.5–1.25) 300mg: 1.0 (0.5–2.00) 450mg: 1.0 (0.75–3.00)	75 mg: 10.15 ± 3.1 150 mg: 10.71 ± 2.0 300 mg: 10.62 ± 1.80 450 mg: 10.85 ± 1.51		
		fed (HF)	339.77**	938.97**	951.78**	–	–		
Abiraterone acetate 18	1000		54.67 ± 68.30	543 ± 169	386.13 ± 266.80 (n = 15)	5.53 (2.67–35.00)	8.98 ± 3.92 (n = 15)		Bouhajib and Tayab (2019)

ESRD: end-stage renal disease, FPAA: fine-particle abiraterone acetate; HF: high-fat meal; HI: hepatic impairment, LF: low-fat meal; MF: medium-fat meal,

* geometric mean with% coefficient of variation in brackets

** geometric mean.

progression-free survival was prolonged from 7.4 months to 12.2 months (hazard ratio 0.55, CI: 0.31 - 0.99, $p = 0.044$). The presence of an exposure-response relationship led to applying this threshold for therapeutic drug monitoring of abiraterone. In a recent review, abiraterone was listed as one of a few oral antineoplastic drugs with a strong recommendation for therapeutic drug monitoring (Mueller-Schoell et al., 2021).

As D4A metabolite also exhibits activity against androgen receptors, researchers investigated how significantly it contributes to the beneficial antitumor effect. Their analysis showed that the D4A concentrations observed in the patients' plasma are too low to effectively inhibit the CYP17A1 enzyme, given an IC₅₀ value of 0.035 ng/mL (Blanchet et al., 2018). Only two subjects out of the cohort comprising 30 individuals had values above the assumed threshold. An additional analysis of the metabolic ratios (D4A/abiraterone) pointed out that an above-average D4A concentration in comparison with the parent entity correlated with shorter progression-free survival (204 vs. 317 days, respectively), as well as overall survival (242 vs. 568 days, respectively). The elevated D4A/abiraterone ratio may reflect the 3 β -HSD activity. As this enzyme is also responsible for creating androstenedione and testosterone, the insufficient inhibition of their synthesis may lead to the failure of the therapy. Further observational studies corroborate these conclusions. An observational study on routinely treated mCRPC patients confirmed that the 8.4 ng/mL threshold of abiraterone concentration was associated with longer progression-free survival in individuals whose abiraterone concentrations exceeded that value (16.9 vs. 6.1 months, $p = 0.077$; hazard ratio 0.44, $p = 0.01$) (van Nuland et al., 2020). At the same time, D4A exposure was not associated with a good response to the treatment.

New findings indicate that chemotherapy pretreatment is a covariate that should be considered when monitoring abiraterone (Boerrigter et al., 2022). When the mCRPC patient did not go through the pretreatment with docetaxel, the 8.4 ng/mL threshold was no longer an indicator of longer survival. If the concentrations were above the threshold, the progression-free and overall survival were 462 and 1067 days, while for the lower concentrations, they were 546 ($p = 0.81$) and 1370 days ($p = 0.58$), respectively. At the same time, abiraterone levels were higher in patients in the early-stage pre-chemotherapy mCRPC than in post-chemotherapy subjects ($C_{min} = 13.5$ ng/mL vs. 9.7 ng/mL, $p = 0.048$).

As stated above, an accurate determination of abiraterone, and

possibly D4A, may lead to optimization of the mCRPC treatment through dose adjustment and other strategies. The applied analytical method should be feasible for routine analysis. For example, the sample volume should be as low as possible, and the method should include as few steps as possible. Numerous methods that allow abiraterone determination have been described; almost all utilize high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Supplementary Data File, Table S1). Most of the methods focus on the determination of abiraterone in human plasma, and few are sensitive enough to capture the prodrug - AA (Bouhajib and Tayab, 2019). Abiraterone levels in clinical samples are low, and the target parameter - C_{trough} , should be above 8.4 ng/mL. Such low levels necessitate tandem mass spectrometers (MS/MS) detection. Yet, sample processing often requires multiple steps, and there is no point-of-care device allowing rapid determination of abiraterone.

5. Reaching the target concentrations - strategies to improve abiraterone bioavailability

An open question in the field of therapeutic drug monitoring is its effectiveness, especially in terms of costs. The monthly financial burden of the abiraterone therapy is considerable, reaching over 8000 USD for a monthly supply as of 2016 (Pilon et al., 2016). Ultimately, the determined concentrations provide useful information to the clinician on what should be the next rational step in the therapy. The personalized approach suggests increasing abiraterone's dose to 1500 mg daily to obtain plasma levels above the recommended 8.4 ng/mL threshold.

However, the higher dose automatically translates to a higher cost of the therapy. A pharmacoeconomic analysis showed that the dose adjustment increased the quality-adjusted life-years by 0.149, but at the same time, it was associated with €22 145 incremental costs (Ten Ham et al., 2021). Therefore, it appears rational to explore strategies to lower the costs while maintaining or increasing the effectiveness of the treatment. The most promising directions are utilizing the food effect and developing innovative formulations (Fig. 2).

5.1. Food effect

Abiraterone exhibits a considerable food effect. The first study describing it reported a 5-fold increase of the AUC after a low-fat meal in healthy volunteers (Chi et al., 2015). A high-fat meal caused an even greater increase in abiraterone exposure, reaching 17-fold the AUC

Table 2

Abiraterone pharmacokinetic parameters in mCRPC patients. For C_{\max} and AUC data are presented as means \pm standard deviations, if available; for t_{\max} data are presented as medians with minimum-maximum range in brackets.

Number of subjects	Dose[mg]	Prandialstate	C_{\max} [ng/ml]	AUC _{0-t} [ng·h/ml]	AUC _{0-∞} [ng·h/ml]	t_{\max} [h]	$t_{1/2}$ [h]	Refs.		
33 (total; 3 - 6 per study group)	250 - 1000	fasted	250 mg:	–	250 mg:	250 mg:	250 mg:	Ryan et al. (2010)		
			283 \pm 142.2	1411 \pm 697.2	2.0 \pm 0	5.3 \pm				
			500 mg:	500 mg:	500 mg:	1.7				
			331 \pm 204.9	1781 \pm 986.8	1.5 \pm 0.5	500 mg:				
			750 mg:	750 mg:	750 mg:	10.6 \pm				
			290 \pm 126.6	1665 \pm 704.6	2.0 \pm 0.1	6.3				
			1000 mg:	1000 mg:	1000 mg:	750 mg:				
		510 \pm 366.5	3478 \pm	1.8 \pm 0.4	7.1 \pm					
			2012.2		3.4					
					1000 mg:					
					14.4 \pm					
					7.7					
				fed	250 mg:	–	250 mg:		125 mg:	125 mg:
					421 \pm 75.8	1387 \pm 290.2	2.0 \pm 0.1		5.1 \pm	
			500 mg:	500 mg:	500 mg:	1.0				
			676 \pm 147.9	3840 \pm	2.7 \pm 1.2	500 mg:				
			750 mg:	1080.9	750 mg:	6.9 \pm				
			1552 \pm 458.1	750 mg:	2.0 \pm 0	5.7				
			1000 mg:	9359 \pm	1000 mg:	750 mg:				
			2194 \pm 1096.9	3338.6	4.0 \pm 0	7.9 \pm				
				1000 mg:		3.4				
				14,404 \pm		1000 mg:				
				5971.0		12.5 \pm				
						1.2				
33	1000/day in 28-day cycles	fasted	Cycle 1, day 1: 182 \pm 254 Cycle 1, day 8: 207 \pm 142 Cycle 2, day 1: 226 \pm 178	Cycle 1, day 1: 675 \pm 725 Cycle 1, day 8: 965 \pm 520 Cycle 2, day 1: 993 \pm 639	–	Cycle 1, day 1: 2 (1–4) Cycle 1, day 8: 2 (1–4) Cycle 2, day 1: 2 (1–6)	–	Tolcher et al. (2012)		
25 (n = 7 fasted, n = 18 HF)	1000	fasted, fed (LF), fed (HF)	modified fasted: 196 (71)/196 (85)* low fat: 265 (71)* high fat: 342 (70)*	modified fasted: 1185 (90)/ 973 (58)* low fat: 1264 (65)* high fat: 1992 (34)*	–	–	–	Chi et al. (2015)		
22	500 - 1000, without or with docetaxel		500 mg: 166 \pm 160/ 69.3 \pm 21.3 1000 mg: 282 \pm 267 With docetaxel: 500 mg: 148 \pm 111/ 114 \pm 64.1 1000 mg: 278 \pm 248	500 mg: 657 \pm 499/ 424 \pm 155 1000 mg: 1138 \pm 697 With docetaxel: 500 mg: 821 \pm 705/ 543 \pm 169 1000 mg: 1385 \pm 1007	–	500 mg: 1.50 (1.50–1.83)/ 1.87 (1.50–1.92) 1000 mg: 1.83 (1.42–1.87) With docetaxel: 500 mg: 1.83 (0.50–6.00)/ 2.00 (1.47–5.10) 1000 mg: 2.95 (1.50–3.50)	–	Tagawa et al. (2016)		
35	1000, with cabazitaxel		217 \pm 159	916 \pm 443	–	2.00 (1.00–6.00)	–	Massard et al. (2017)		
12	500 (fed) or 1000 (fasted)	fasted	148 (98–223)*	776 (514–1172)*	–	–	–	Lubberman et al. (2019)		
		fed (CB)	152 (99–235)*	686 (455–1035)*	–	–	–			

CB: continental breakfast; HF: high-fat meal; LF: low-fat meal;

* geometric mean with 90% confidence interval in brackets.

value reported after a fasted administration and over 7-fold for C_{\max} . Of note, this positive effect was less pronounced in mCRPC patients. While a high-fat meal increased the AUC two-fold, the exposures after a low-fat meal and in the fasted state were similar. The timing of the meal also plays a significant role. A meal eaten even one hour post-dose can increase both C_{\max} and AUC of abiraterone (Inoue et al., 2015). The greatest effects were observed for regimens including a meal two hours prior to AA administration, which led to a \sim 10-fold increase in C_{\max} and

\sim 7-fold increase in AUC. These findings led to the exploration of the causes of the food effect and its possible utilization in therapy optimization.

An altered solubility in fed and fasted intestinal fluids causes the distinct postprandial behavior of abiraterone acetate. In fed intestinal fluids (FeSSIF and pooled FeHIF), the thermodynamic solubility of AA was $306 \pm 5 \mu\text{M}$ and $84 \pm 11 \mu\text{M}$, respectively (Geboers et al., 2016). These values are considerably higher than in fluids reflecting the fasted

Fig. 2. Strategies for optimization of abiraterone acetate therapy.

state (FaSSIF and pooled FaHIF): $64.6 \pm 5.2 \mu\text{M}$ and $37.4 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{M}$, respectively (Stappaerts et al., 2015). Abiraterone, a product of AA hydrolysis catalyzed by intestinal esterases, also dissolves better in the fed fluids. Its thermodynamic solubility in fasted fluids was $12.7 \pm 4.2 \mu\text{M}$ for FaSSIF and $3.1 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$ for FaHIF, respectively; in comparison, the solubility in FeSSIF was $36 \pm 5 \mu\text{M}$ and in FeHIF $74 \pm 6 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. Of note, *in vivo* fasted state experiments showed that the intraluminal abiraterone concentrations exceed their thermodynamic solubility, but this effect is most probably limited to the proximal part of the intestine (Stappaerts et al., 2015). As the supersaturation is a metastable state, precipitation is imminent. Both biological and artificial fed state intestinal fluids differ from the fasted ones; they have higher bile salt and phospholipid concentration, higher osmolality and buffer capacity, and lower pH (Dahlgren et al., 2021). Thus, the higher bile salt content promotes micelle formation which increases the solubilization capacity. It increases the solubility of both AA and abiraterone and extends the release of the compound in the distal parts of the gastrointestinal tract (Geboers et al., 2016).

Increased solubility in fed intestinal fluids and increased bioavailability under fed conditions led to an investigation if this effect could be employed in the dosing regimen. A widely discussed clinical trial prospectively evaluated if such an altered administration was comparable to the standard 1000 mg AA fasted dosing (Szmulewitz et al., 2018). This multicenter study included 72 mCRPC patients randomly assigned to either a standard regimen - 1000 mg AA fasted - or a modified regimen - 250 mg AA with a low-fat meal. The study's endpoint was a change in serum PSA within a 12-week therapy, but the authors also compared abiraterone pharmacokinetics. Based on the primary endpoint, the modified regimen was non-inferior to the standard approach, as the serum PSA decreased to a similar degree (mean log change -1.59 vs. -1.19 for the modified and standard treatments, respectively). On the other hand, the pharmacokinetics differed significantly between the two strategies. C_{max} and C_{trough} were greater for the standard treatment than the modified one, as was the between-subject variability. Although the results provide an interesting insight into the disposition of abiraterone acetate, it is still questionable whether a sparse-sampling design, such as the one utilized in the study above, can accurately capture the clearance values and estimate the food effects (Li et al., 2015). Nevertheless, these clinical observations created a foothold for further exploration of a modified food regimen as a method of AA dose reduction.

The next prospective trial summarized the data from 12 mCRPC patients in a cross-over design (Lubberman et al., 2019). During the experiment, each patient completed two-week long treatments with a standard AA dose fasted or 500 mg AA with a continental breakfast. Abiraterone C_{max} after a reduced dose was 152 mg/L and $\text{AUC}_{0-24 \text{ h}}$ was

686 mg-h/L; these values were similar to the two-fold greater dose but administered in the fasted state - C_{max} was 148 mg/L, while the $\text{AUC}_{0-24 \text{ h}}$ was 776 mg-h/L. However, when the researchers evaluated geometric means and confidence intervals, the two regimens were not bioequivalent. The geometric mean for the AUC was 0.88 (90% confidence interval (CI) 0.73 - 1.07), and for the C_{max} it was 1.03 (90% CI 0.79 - 1.34). The worst ratio was reported for C_{trough} : 0.81 (90% CI 0.60-1.10). Given these results, the authors ceased further enrollment. Although the bioequivalence test failed, the modified diet approach could still be implemented in a hospital setting on the condition of abiraterone concentration monitoring. Another finding of the study was that taking AA with food modestly increased patients' satisfaction with the treatment. Therefore, the modified administration can increase compliance. The altered regimen is already being put to practice in some countries. A recent study discussed the results of a survey conducted among Indian oncologists (Patel et al., 2020). 75% of the 251 surveyed physicians were aware of the possible dose reduction, and 62% had already put it into practice. Most commonly, the switch was dictated by the patient's limited resources. The study mentioned above estimated the yearly cost savings if all Indian mCRPC patients switched to a reduced AA dose with food. According to their calculations, the yearly savings would reach up to 180 million USD.

Another study focused on the effectiveness of the "food intervention" combined with therapeutic drug monitoring (Groenland et al., 2020). In this trial, 32 eligible patients followed the standard AA dosing regimen: 1000 mg in the modified fasted state. Then, abiraterone concentrations were determined in samples drawn 4, 8, and 12 weeks after commencing the treatment. The physicians adjusted the therapy according to the abiraterone concentration. If the C_{trough} was below 8.4 ng/mL, the patients had to take abiraterone with a light meal or a snack; high-fat foods were not recommended. If this modification did not give satisfactory results, the AA dose increased to 1250 or 1500 mg. As much as 63% of the patients had low abiraterone concentrations at the first time point. The modification had positive outcomes: 16 out of 20 patients with suboptimal exposure reached the desired C_{trough} threshold, and only one remained unresponsive to the treatment. Of note, the food intervention caused greater variability in the measured concentrations in comparison with the values recorded before. The authors suggested that one of the causes might be non-standardized meals. Another question is the applicability and cost-effectiveness of such an approach. The authors noted that the patients who required the modified treatment still had shorter progression-free survival than those with adequate C_{trough} values. The same research group explored the aspect of food intervention combined with therapeutic drug monitoring (Ten Ham et al., 2021). They estimated that the administration of AA with a snack in patients

who did not achieve adequate C_{trough} had an 81.9% likelihood of being cost-effective. At the same time, solely increasing the dose had higher incremental costs and only an 8.04% likelihood of being cost-effective.

The main concern with the modified dosing regimen is the control over the meal composition in an outpatient setting. If the fat content significantly impacts the AA bioavailability, the patient would be encouraged to keep a consistent diet. Otherwise, the drug exposure would greatly fluctuate and impact the treatment outcomes. Therefore, the manufacturer decided to recommend the administration to the fasted state only.

5.2. Novel formulations

All of the studies cited in the previous chapter took advantage of the food effect to increase the exposure to abiraterone. The other path to augment response to abiraterone is to develop novel formulations with an increased bioavailability in the fasted state and thus mitigated food effect. Such medicinal products that offer advantages over the originator in terms of pharmacokinetic profile, safety, or stability are labeled supergenerics (Singh, 2018). Several strategies allow for reaching this goal. The main ones are decreasing the particle size, introducing amorphous forms, adding lipid-based agents, and adding absorption enhancers.

The first FDA-approved novel AA formulation is YONSA, introduced in 2018 (U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2018). YONSA is based on the SoluMatrix Fine Particle Technology™, previously used in several products with non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (Argoff et al., 2016; Hussaini et al., 2016). This technological platform creates fine drug particles through dry milling (iCeutica, 2022). The submicron particles, 200 - 800 nm in diameter, created during milling are also protected from agglomeration. The small diameter was shown as a key factor that increased the bioavailability of AA in a study on healthy volunteers (Goldwater et al., 2017). The study comprised two stages. First, the researchers performed a dose-escalation study with 100, 200, and 400 mg of the fine particle AA; then, additional doses of 125, 500, and 625 mg of fine particle AA were tested against 1000 mg of the originator (Zytiga) in the fasted state. All the main parameters, AUC and C_{max} , increased proportionally with the administered dose of the novel formulation. The most comparable dose with the 1000 mg of the originator administered in the fasted state was 500 mg. The $AUC_{0-\infty}$ of the competitor was 438.02 ng·h/mL and 453.2 ng·h/mL for the originator; C_{max} was 84.2 ng/mL and 83.4 ng/mL for the fine-particle formulation and the originator, respectively. The 90% confidence intervals of the geometric mean ratios were within 0.8 - 1.25 interval, indicating bioequivalence of 500 mg of the novel formulation to 1000 mg of Zytiga. The food effect for YONSA was also evaluated in a cross-over study in healthy volunteers (Papangelou et al., 2017). A high-fat standardized meal eaten 30 min before drug administration significantly increased the bioavailability of the fine-particle formulation. The geometric mean ratios of AUC_{0-t} and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ for the fed vs. fasted conditions were 442.4 and 458.6%, respectively. The ratio for C_{max} was 649.5%. While the greater exposure did not cause serious adverse effects, the study results indicate that the novel formulation is also prone to food effects. YONSA was also tested in a clinical setting in patients with mCRPC. A study with a one-year follow-up compared serum testosterone and PSA levels between the two arms of the study: four 125 mg YONSA tablets with 4 mg methylprednisolone or four 250 mg Zytiga tablets with 5 mg prednisolone (Chapas-Reed et al., 2020; Stein et al., 2018). The first stage focused on the initial three months of the treatment (Stein et al., 2018). During this time, the fine-particulate formulation was as effective as the originator. Moreover, the C_{trough} values were comparable between the two study groups. When the observation was prolonged for one year, both treatment groups maintained the desired testosterone-suppressing effect, with similar safety and the rate of adverse events (Chapas-Reed et al., 2020).

Another approach relied on a nano-amorphous formulation

produced with a continuous flow technology (Solymosi et al., 2017a). In contrast to the SoluMatrix platform, the preparation of this formulation relied on the precipitation of AA from an organic solvent. The process involved Soluplus, a polymer acting as a solubilizer, proprietary to BASF (BASF Pharma, 2022). It allowed obtaining size distribution with d50 and d90 values of 186 nm and 254 nm, which was significantly smaller than the unformulated AA (particle size of 50 - 100 μm) or a wet-milled formulation (d50 and d90 values of 497 nm and 1050 nm, respectively) (Solymosi et al., 2017b). As a result, the solubility of AA increased significantly in biorelevant media in comparison with the original drug formulation. For Zytiga, the solubility in FaSSiF was 0.018 mg/mL and in FeSSiF it was 0.159 mg/mL; for the nano-amorphous AA the solubilities were 0.158 mg/mL and 0.480 mg/mL for FaSSiF and FeSSiF, respectively. Preliminary studies in beagle dogs showed that the novel formulation should also resist the food effect. In the next stage, the formulation was tested on ten healthy volunteers (Solymosi et al., 2017a). The administration schedule involved 100 or 200 mg of a powder-in-bottle investigational product under fasting conditions or 200 mg of the product after a standardized meal. The exposure in fasted conditions was less-than-proportional, as the AUC increased by approximately 38% and the C_{max} by 45%. Surprisingly, co-administration of the novel product with food decreased the exposure. The decrease was 59% for C_{max} and 26% for AUC. Comparison with the historical data for Zytiga indicated reduced interpatient variability. These promising results led to the development of a novel tablet designed as an oral suspension (Jordán et al., 2021). A recently published study described the clinical trial of Zytiga 1000 mg vs. 250 mg of the novel formulation. Both were tested in the fasted and fed states. The food effect was examined under a modified fasting state for Zytiga and after an FDA standard high-fat breakfast for the test formulation. All the oral suspension strengths achieved maximum concentrations rapidly ($t_{\text{max}} = 0.5$ h) compared to Zytiga ($t_{\text{max}} = 1.5$ h in the fasting and 3.0 h in the modified fasting conditions). Also, the study confirmed a significant negative food effect for the novel formulation observed in preclinical investigations. Previous results predicted that the 250 mg AA in the novel formulation should be equivalent to 1000 mg Zytiga. In reality, the novel formulation had significantly greater overall exposure in the fasting conditions, reaching even 300% greater values for C_{max} than the originator. But for the high-fat breakfast administration, the authors claimed bioequivalence with 1000 mg Zytiga in the fasted state. The reported 90% CI were 96.61 - 151.82 for C_{max} ($p = 0.16$), 79.21 - 105.10 for AUC_{0-t} ($p = 0.28$), and 78.65 - 104.05 for $AUC_{0-\infty}$ ($p = 0.24$). However, if Zytiga was given in the modified-fasted conditions, abiraterone exposure was significantly greater. Neither of the prandial conditions tested in the trial allowed obtaining acceptable exposure for the novel product. For example, the ratio for the AUC did not exceed 20% of the values registered for the modified-fasted administration of Zytiga. What is important in the light of therapeutic drug monitoring, the mean abiraterone concentration at 24 h after administration of the 250 mg suspension was below values determined for the originator at the same time point (2.80 ng/mL vs. 3.89 ng/mL, respectively). However, the formulation is promising due to increased bioavailability, lower variability, and a more convenient form for dysphagia patients.

The positive impact of Soluplus may involve not only increased dissolution but also an effective inhibition of precipitation in the gastrointestinal tract. Boleslavská et al. (2020b) tested the potential of several polymeric excipients to inhibit the precipitation of AA from a supersaturated solution. The rationale of the design relied on the assumption that AA dissolves already in the stomach and may precipitate after transitioning to the more basic intestinal fluids; the greater the supersaturation, the more pronounced precipitation. In the experiment, Soluplus, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, and hydroxypropyl cellulose were potent precipitation inhibitors in media simulating fasted intestinal fluid. The authors developed two candidate formulations by spray drying, both containing amorphous AA. The first formulation (T1) comprised precipitation inhibitors, while the second one (T2) offered a

“tuned” release. The polymer chosen for the second formulation dissolved poorly in the acidic media. Therefore, it could prevent the excessive release of AA in the stomach and the subsequent precipitation. The authors tested their formulations *in vivo* in an animal model under fasting conditions. They compared T1 and T2 against Zytiga and the reference Soluplus-based formulation. Both novel formulations were superior to the originator and the reference, leading to over 100% increase in bioavailability over Zytiga. Of note, the T2 prototype had the highest measured concentrations at the last time point, 4 h after administration. In the light of C_{trough} as the therapeutic target, such a prolonged release might be a favorable option. However, the formulations were not tested in humans, and the clinical efficacy of such a modified release product would have to be confirmed.

Besides Soluplus, certain emulsifiers can increase AA solubility and bioavailability. Schultz et al. (2020) created formulations with Capmul PG8 and Capmul MCM, mono- and diglyceride emulsifiers (ABITEC, 2022). Their strategy relied on silica-lipid hybrids and supersaturated silica-lipid hybrids. The dissolution results showed that these formulations effectively increase solubility compared to Zytiga, but the effect depends on the nature of the emulsifier and the drug load. The highest solubility was obtained for a formulation with Capmul PG8 and AA load, reaching 90% equilibrium solubility. None of the supersaturated formulations, in which the drug load was above 100% of the equilibrium solubility, released a greater fraction of the drug. The effect was sustained in dissolution experiments with lipases. According to the authors, the underperformance of supersaturated hybrids was due to the partial crystallization of AA. Another promising aspect of the novel lipid-based formulations was a similar dissolution characteristic in biorelevant media simulating fed and fasted states. Although the authors did not perform any *in silico* simulations or pre-clinical evaluation, there is a potential for a dosage form with minimum or negligible food effect. Boleslavská et al. also investigated lipid-based formulations (Boleslavská et al., 2020a). They developed formulations based on “liquid marbles” to mitigate limited AA bioavailability in the fasted state. The marbles contained a lipid-based core surrounded by a shell of solid particles. The shell protects the core from evaporation and leakage and also prevents particle agglomeration. The formulations contained mixtures of synthetic (Capmul or Capryol) lipids, castor oil, and compatible surfactants. The most promising candidate, oil marbles based on Capmul oil and Kolliphor as a surfactant, was then encapsulated and tested in rats against Zytiga. Under fasting conditions, the test formulation increased bioavailability two-fold. The authors also evaluated the food effect for both test and reference. While for Zytiga, the exposure increased significantly in fed conditions, the effect was not observed for the oil marbles. The only difference for the test product was faster t_{max} : 125 min in fasting conditions vs. 152 min in fed conditions.

Liquisolid compacts offer another approach for utilizing lipids to improve abiraterone’s dissolution and solubilization characteristics. Dahiya et al. (2021) used olive oil as a vehicle, as it offered the highest solubility of AA both in pure oil and when mixed with biorelevant dissolution media. The lipid particles were coated in silicon dioxide, mixed with other excipients, which included surfactants, and press-punched into tablets. The addition of olive oil allowed molecular dispersion and prevented AA from crystallization; the effect was sustained for six months. Nevertheless, the authors did not evaluate the *in vivo* performance of their dosage form. Instead, they developed an *in silico* model and utilized it to fine-tune the development process with a Central Composite Design. Their goal was to minimize the food effect. The simulations suggested that the 190 mg AA dose of the liquisolid formulation should be the most comparable to 1000 mg Zytiga and, at the same time, exhibit an approximately 10% increase in the exposure between the fasted and fed states.

Lastly, the addition of absorption enhancers can help overcome the unfavorable food effect and increase abiraterone concentrations. A recent study described the development and performance of a novel formulation co-formulated with SNAC: sodium N-(8-[2-

hydroxybenzoyl] amino) caprylate (Feng et al., 2022). The exact mechanism of action of SNAC remains unclear. One hypothesis states that SNAC allows a transcellular lipophilic pathway across the small intestinal epithelium (Alani and Robinson, 2008). Another study showed that SNAC changes the cellular membrane, effectively fluidizing it and allowing transport (Twarog et al., 2020). Interestingly, it did not affect the paracellular pathway. SNAC is already being used in marketed products, such as Rybelsus (semaglutide) or Eligen B₁₂ (Cyanocobalamin), so it was a good candidate for improving abiraterone bioavailability in fasted conditions. Feng et al. (Feng et al., 2022) conducted a three-phase open-label clinical trial with the novel AA formulation that contained AA and SNAC. They investigated dose escalation and bioequivalence under fasting conditions and compared food effects between the test and reference (Zytiga) formulations. According to the authors, abiraterone exposure increased proportionally within the administered dose range: 75, 150, 300, or 450 mg. Under fasting conditions, the 300 mg strength was shown to be bioequivalent to 1000 mg Zytiga, with the following ratios: C_{max} 106.62 (90% CI: 95.73 - 118.760), AUC_{0-t} 94.01 (90% CI: 87.42 - 101.10), and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ 92.38 (90% CI: 86.00 - 99.23). The novel formulation was still prone to food effects. When administered after a high-fat meal, the C_{max} and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ increased over two-fold. Still, the effect is less pronounced than for the originator, where the modified fed administration increased C_{max} 5.89 times and $AUC_{0-\infty}$ 4.3 times. Most importantly, the novel formulation had a similar safety profile to the originator, and the addition of SNAC did not interact with prednisone, which is co-administered with AA.

6. Future directions for research

Current recommendations specify an abiraterone plasma concentration of 8.4 ng/mL as a threshold below which the probability of a shorter survival time increases. The first logical choice in case of insufficient exposure would be increasing the dose of AA. But the clinical trials with a high dose AA, 1000 mg BID, showed this solution has limited clinical utility, as the treatment outcomes are similar to the standard schedule (Friedlander et al., 2017). Therefore, there is a need to overcome low exposure, achieve the concentrations recommended in the therapeutic monitoring, halt the progression, and prolong the survival. One such approach would be to investigate the previously described “food intervention” further. As the Zytiga product information states that it must not be taken with food (European Medicines Agency, 2018), taking the drug with a snack can be seen as an off-label recommendation. Yet, the National Comprehensive Cancer Network mentioned the possibility of modified dosing (250 mg with food) in their 2019 guidelines (Mohler et al., 2019). The long-term efficacy and therapeutic equivalence have still not been determined in large-scale clinical trials. Next, many novel supra-bioavailable formulations have not been cleared for the market yet. As some of them may allow achieving higher exposure in a fasted state, they seem to be a promising first-choice option to ensure the therapy’s success. Still, clinical trials will have to assure that increased AA solubility from these products translates to comparable long-term efficacy to Zytiga.

Another problematic issue is that as much as one-third of the patients present primary resistance to abiraterone, and most patients acquire resistance to the treatment within a year (Buttiglierio et al., 2015). A solution to a potential resistance can lead through the path of altering abiraterone metabolism. SRD5A enzyme converts D4A, the active metabolite of abiraterone, to 5- α -abiraterone (Li et al., 2015b). The latter allegedly has tumor-promoting properties due to its androgen-receptor agonist activity. Li et al. (2016) suggested that circumventing this reaction by adding an SRD5A inhibitor such as dutasteride should decline the conversion yield, leading to increased exposure to abiraterone. This hypothesis was recently tested in two mCRPC patients with reported abiraterone resistance (Lian et al., 2020). In both patients, the concentrations of 5- α -abiraterone markedly decreased after the introduction of dutasteride; at the same time, abiraterone

concentrations increased. This slight modification of the treatment either reduced PSA levels or halted its increase.

Finally, the aspect worth investigating is the rationale of the current concentration threshold for therapeutic drug monitoring. A novel *in vitro* study investigated the abiraterone affinity to CYP17A1 (Cheong et al., 2020). The authors studied the residence time of abiraterone within the enzyme's active site. The *in silico* simulations indicated that the slow and tight-binding inhibition of CYP17A1 by abiraterone sustains even after the molecule was almost completely washed out from the plasma. These findings contrast the initially approved dosing regimen and signalize that a lower dose (500 mg) may be as effective as the currently used one. Such a change in the treatment algorithm would be beneficial from a financial point of view. Also, the risk of concentration-dependent adverse effects would diminish. However, the authors performed *in vitro* experiments and *in silico* simulations; therefore, their observations are not straightforwardly reflected in the *in vivo* trials.

7. Conclusions

The findings summarized herein show that there is a space for improvement even for established drug formulations - and abiraterone acetate seems to be a good example of that. As AA is a BCS class IV compound, its poor solubility and limited bioavailability coupled with high intersubject variability may cause difficulties in achieving a desired therapeutic effect. The first option for improving the treatment outcome is therapeutic drug monitoring. Applying sufficiently sensitive analytical methods can minimize the risk of failure because the clinicians can adjust the regimen accordingly. Because abiraterone has a large positive food effect, co-administration with food can be used to increase exposure without increasing the dose and treatment costs. Another option discussed in this review is the development of so-called supergenerics of abiraterone acetate, which allow reaching similar concentrations and pharmacodynamic effects with a decreased dose and at a lower price point when compared to the original formulation. Ultimately, a combination of these approaches can be used for patients' benefit.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dorota Danielak: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Tereza Krejčí:** Writing – review & editing. **Josef Beránek:** Writing – review & editing.

Supplementary materials

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